

The applicability of social marketing in the uptake of bio-energy based technologies.

Marcel Maré^{1,3}, Harold J Annegarn^{2,1}

¹*SeTAR Centre, University of Johannesburg, Bunting Road Campus,*

²*Department of Geography, Environmental Management and Energy Studies; and*

³*Tshwane University of Technology, PO Box 14703, Hatfield, 0028, South Africa*

E-mail: marem1969@gmail.com

Abstract

Social marketing has been widely applied for more than three decades in the fields of public health and the environment with significant success, for example the use of contraceptives, oral rehydration therapy and malaria prevention. From examination of descriptions of previous improved bio-energy based technology implementation projects it becomes apparent that social marketing principles were absent in many of the unsuccessful bio-energy projects. The misconception is often that all that is required by the project team is to provide information or change beliefs (equating marketing with advertising) without asking whether these activities are likely to lead to the desired behavioural change. This paper reviews the applicability of social marketing in the uptake of bio-energy based technologies and evaluates the extent to which elements of social marketing strategies were utilised in the Sub-Saharan region. It distinguishes between the practice of commercial marketing, whose goal is profit, and the practice of social marketing, whose goal is societal benefit. Issues of sustainability, segmentation of markets, differences in behavioral characteristics, and indigenous cultural influences are discussed. The review evaluates studies of the dissemination of specific bio-energy based technological programmes in the Sub-Saharan region. We argue that social marketing represents a viable companion to other strategies in the dissemination of bio-energy based technologies in the Southern African region.

Keywords:

social marketing, bio-energy, technology, stoves, sub-Saharan Africa.

1. INTRODUCTION

To achieve the millennium development goals (MDGs) for the Southern African region, a significant change in energy use patterns in a relatively short period of time is required. The large-scale burning of biomass is a threat to biodiversity and directly impacts human development levels. It has been demonstrated that household-by-household adoption and sustained use of safe, inexpensive and energy efficient stove designs can make a significant contribution towards these goals (Bailis et al., 2003), in particular reducing carbon emission levels and the sustainable use of renewable resources. Several improved stoves have been developed and introduced into developing countries over the past decades (e.g. review by (Karekezi & Ranja, 1997; Karekezi et al., 2004). However, widespread uptake of these stoves in their intended target markets has met with limited success (Tucker, 1984; Sharma, 1993; Koshy, 1994; Kuhnenn, 2003; Karve, 2005). Diffusion of the products into the market often ceases once donor aid for the stove project comes to an end (Walubengo, 1988;

Koshy C, 1994; Owsianowski and Barry, 2007). The challenge remains on how to introduce improved stoves into the market (specifically the African market) for the external aims of protecting biodiversity (forest conservation), climate protection (reduced greenhouse gas emissions) and poverty reduction (energy efficiency and safety in the home), with a significant uptake within communities (>50%), without ongoing external donor aid to support the production and marketing of the devices.

2. SOCIAL MARKETING: AN OVERVIEW

Marketing is a social and managerial process by which individuals and groups obtain what they want and need through creating and exchanging products and value with others. Within the marketing environment, social marketing is a form of public-private partnership that uses commercial marketing approaches but with the motive of financial profit balanced against social and environmental considerations (Andreasen, 1995). To be sustainable, such exchanges must be mutually beneficial. Economic

prosperity depends on the generation of such exchanges, assuming the *Chartered Institute of Marketing* definition of 'profitability' can be defined in a non-accounting sense (e.g. benefit or value). All the definitions emphasize the generation of value. Value is the benefit each partner in the exchange seeks (e.g. money, support, prestige, social upliftment) thus driving the exchange process (Kotler et al., 1999).

The same marketing principles used to sell products to consumers can thus also be used to "sell" ideas, attitudes and behaviors (Kotler and Zaltman, 1971). In other words, social marketing differs from other marketing disciplines with respect to its goals and objectives, the overriding aim being behavioural change in the target market as opposed to purely profit driven motives (Andreasen, 1995).

Social marketing focuses on effecting behavioural change in a community. A major shortcoming of a wide range of social marketing programs in the field is that, though their project managers consider themselves at least in part social marketers, they fail to keep their eye on the main goal of changing behaviour. The misconception is often that all they must do is provide information to change beliefs. Sometimes they think this way because they were trained in other disciplines and tend to equate marketing with advertising. So they think their goal is to "get the word out" or to "change attitudes" without asking whether either of these activities is likely to lead to the desired behaviour. They seem to assume that this will happen in some mystical "long run" (Andreasen, 1994). The behavioural analysis approach in social marketing is founded on the behavioural sciences as conceptualised and researched by B.F. Skinner. Experimental behaviour analysis, and later applied behaviour analysis, emerged from Skinner's research and teaching. He laid the groundwork for numerous therapies and interventions to improve the quality of life of individuals, groups, and entire communities (Geller, 2002).

The primary emphasis of marketing is thus to make an organisation customer-focused. In practice the formulation of a marketing strategy precedes the product development phase. At the outset a *Macro Environmental Analysis* is undertaken, evaluating the political, economic, social, cultural, technological, industry-specific and market factors that could be of relevance. The outcome of this analysis is used to build a marketing strategy, blending the various factors, variables and categories into a "*Marketing-Mix*". There are some important differences between social and commercial marketing, specifically: the products tend to be more complex, demand is more varied, target groups are more challenging to reach, consumer involvement is more intense and the competition is more subtle and varied (Kotler et al., 1999).

3. SOCIAL MARKETING IN PRACTICE

Social marketing strategies have been used successfully in Sub-Saharan Africa, for example the use of contraceptives and oral rehydration therapy (Black and Harvey, 1976; Dougherty et al., 2004), malaria prevention and HIV/AIDS prevention.

3.1 Social marketing of insecticide-treated nets

It has been established that insecticide-treated nets have proven efficacy as a malaria-control tool in Africa, yet effectiveness cannot be taken for granted. Social marketing of insecticide-treated nets showed great potential for effective malaria control in rural African settings, shown for example in a southern Tanzanian study in two rural districts (Schellenberg et al., 2001).

Socially marketed nets were introduced over a two-year period, in a population of 480 000 people. Insecticide-treated net coverage of infants rose from less than 10% at baseline to more than 50% three years later. This programme was associated with a 27% increase in survival rates of children under four years old. Coverage in such children was higher in areas with longer access to the programme. The modest average coverage achieved by 1999 in the two districts (18% of children younger than 5 years) suggests that insecticide-treated nets prevented one in twenty child deaths during the two-year period.

Large-scale net manufacturers in Tanzania sell their products through wholesalers to shopkeepers and petty traders in remote rural areas, so that untreated nets are not uncommon: nationwide, 13–17% of rural households with children were using nets in 1999. However prices are commonly inflated, compromising quality, and there has been no continued distribution of insecticide for nets (Schellenberg et al., 2001).

The most common marketing strategy involves subsidies to make insecticide-treated nets more affordable and accessible. This can however lead to damaging market distortions. In the Gambia, treated nets were distributed free of charge by regional health teams, leading to improved child survival. However, when the subsidies were discontinued, people were unwilling to pay for services that had once been free, and mortality rates returned to their previous levels (D'Alessandro et al., 1995).

3.2 Social Marketing and HIV

In Tanzania HIV/AIDS education and social marketing condom promotion campaigns occurred over a four-year period, so as to assess changes in sexual risk behaviour in Tanzania. The process of exposure to AIDS education messages and exposure to the specific brand advertising for the "Salama" brand of condoms was very different. While exposure to AIDS education was early and gradual,

exposure to Salama brand condoms started later, but was much more rapid in its uptake. After one year of advertising, over half of the target population had been reached by the condom advertising campaign, mostly through newspapers, radio and television. During the study period, condom use increased from 15% to 42%. The results further showed that men who adopted condom use did not return to more risky behaviour after completion of the period, which suggests that behavioural change was achieved in the study (Eloundou-Enyegue and Meekers, 2004).

In South Africa, an evaluation of a social marketing intervention targeted at gold miners in the Welkom area showed significant increases in awareness of the personal risk of contracting HIV/AIDS, reductions in the number of sexual partners, and increases in the prevalence of condom use with all partners during the intervention period (D. Meekers, 2000).

A further study, carried out by the Zambia Social Marketing Project, evaluated sexual activity and condom use in Lusaka. The results of the study showed a strong association between a specific brand advertising message and condom use, regardless of educational level. This strongly suggests that condom use in Lusaka has increased substantially as a result of social marketing strategies (Agha, 1991).

4. SOCIAL MARKETING IN IMPROVED STOVE PROJECTS IN SUB-SAHARAN AFRICA

A large number of stove programmes have been launched over the past thirty years. The vast majority of these stove projects failed primarily due to a lack of existing stove markets, lack of attention to consumer needs and a lack of attention to commercial approaches. However, not all failed (Barnes et al., 1993).

The initial wave of stove projects in Sub-Saharan Africa focused on health aspects. The general objective was to uplift the living conditions of the poor in the developing world (Karekezi and Ranja, 1997). Attention subsequently shifted to the potential for saving biomass fuels and limiting deforestation. Currently, there is a refocus on the health-related aspects of improved stove programs, as public health specialists increasingly stress the benefits of moving from traditional stoves to improved stoves. Social marketing factors affecting the target market such as cooking comfort, convenience, and safety in the use of the stoves are starting to receive attention (Ergeneman, 2003).

4.1 The Kenyan Experience

The Kenyan improved cooking stove initiatives began as a relatively self sufficient national production and dissemination infrastructure for higher efficiency charcoal

stoves, with non governmental organisations such as the GTZ (Gesellschaft für Technische Zusammenarbeit) and the ITDG (Intermediate Technology Development Group) acting as technological and developmental intermediaries. This infrastructure was then utilized in the dissemination of efficient wood burning stoves and charcoal kilns. In this process women groups and individuals were trained in the stove production, leaving institutional knowledge and ongoing stove production as a legacy (Chavangi, 1995).

4.1.1 The Jiko Stove Project

The ceramic *Jiko Stove* has been the most successful implementation in Kenya, its success being attributed in part to the attention being paid to applicable marketing and dissemination strategies. Cooperation with producers enabled the establishment of viable marketing and distribution networks and ensured a consistency in the build-quality of the stoves. This built confidence among consumers, but also producers in their income generating potential. As part of the marketing strategy in Kenya wealthier households were targeted at first. This might appear counter-intuitive, yet as producers and marketers grew their business and achieved economies of scale, the prices started to drop, achieving market penetration among all the other urban segments. By the year 2002, the Jiko charcoal stove initiative had achieved a penetration rate of around 50%, while the firewood-based version on the other hand still languished around 5% penetration. This poor performance has been attributed to lack of incentive to save fuel wood apart from where it is already scarce. The Jiko appears, however, to be a Kenyan phenomenon, with attempts to introduce it in Tanzania and Rwanda meeting with failure (Karekezi, 2002; Theuri, 2005).

4.1.2 The Upesi Stove Project

While the penetration of wood stoves in the rural areas has been poor generally, the *Upesi Stove* project has achieved significant results. The Upesi is a simple, improved single-pot stove with a fired ceramic liner installed in the home using mud mortar. The flames are enclosed in the fire area, directing more energy from the fire to cooking, and also producing less smoke and better fuel efficiency.

Given the difficulties faced in disseminating the Upesi Stove (formerly known as the *Maendeleo Stove*) in rural areas, the stove development partners renamed the stove 'Upesi' meaning 'Quick' in Swahili, and promoted its commercial production, with particular attention given to the development of a commercial market for the stoves and its producers. Annual production was estimated at over 12,000 Upesi stoves with women groups able to generate an income from the production and sale of the stoves (Khennas et al., 1999).

The Upesi Social Marketing strategy demonstrated the ability to establish rural commercial networks for domestic

stove dissemination. It showed that it is possible to establish group organisation, business management and marketing training in the rural African context. Furthermore it established that the market-led research, design and production of appropriate stoves was feasible. The training of women in product development, particularly and the principles of stove design also met a measure of success.

Participation in the Upesi project tended to be 'demand-driven' to the extent that local women groups were driving the process in the presence of enabling market conditions set up by the project partners. Project staff then trained the local groups in stove manufacture and provided some logistical support toward the establishment of local supply chains for marketing and sales of the stoves. Once a stove project had been established in a particular location, the women groups in the region were expected to 'own' the enterprise and expanded it as far as is possible (Chavangi, 1995).

The project has, however, met with limited success when attempting mass uptake. When donor funding was withdrawn, interest and participation levels dropped significantly. This raises the question whether the economic, social and cultural realities have been properly researched. Household energy use cannot be isolated from the complex web of economic, social and cultural factors that cause inefficient use of fuel wood. Issues of poverty and food insecurity are but a few of factors at work. Factors such as environmental degradation and health need to be seen in the context of the wider socio-economic factors affecting behaviour. Local participating groups mostly accepted the Upesi stove for different reasons than those originally provided by the implementing organization, suggesting that the programme may benefit from a more comprehensive and integrated social marketing approach (Chavangi, 1995; Theuri, 2005).

5. CONCLUSION

Common to all projects reviewed is the lack of proper social marketing strategies, the exceptions being the Kenyan example. The Jiko Stove has been the most widely accepted *Improved Cooking Stove* (ICS) to date, having achieved the highest penetration of any improved stove in Africa. The need for a proper marketing strategy is often realised by the proponents only at the end of a project and an ad-hoc strategy then belatedly formulated (Ballard-Tremeer and Jawurek, 1996; Karekezi and Ranja, 1997; Kuhnhenh, 2003). This paper is part of ongoing research at the stove design section of the SeTAR centre in South Africa, a multi-disciplinary energy research facility at the University of Johannesburg, housed within the Department of Industrial Design and the Department of Geography, Environmental Management and Energy Studies. It is proposed that the development and integration of successful

social marketing strategies in the energy efficient stove projects in Sub-Saharan Africa is of great relevance to the goals identified by the Peoples Energy Network (PEN).

6. REFERENCES

- Agha, S. (1991), Sexual activity and condom use in Lusaka, Zambia, *International Family Planning Perspectives*, 24(1), 32-37.
- Andreasen, A. (1994), Social marketing: Its definition and domain, *Journal of Public Policy & Marketing*, 13(1), 108-114.
- Andreasen, A. (1995), *Marketing social change: changing behavior to promote health, social development, and the environment*, 1st ed., Jossey-Bass, San Francisco.
- Bailis, R., M. Ezzati, and D. Kammen (2003), Greenhouse gas implications of household energy technology in Kenya, *Environmental science & technology*, 37(10), 2051-2059.
- Ballard-Tremeer, G., and H. Jawurek (1996), Comparison Of Five Rural, Wood-Burning Cooking Devices: Efficiencies And Emissions, *Biomass and Bioenergy*, 11(5), 419-430.
- Barnes, D. F., K. Openshaw, K. R. Smith, and R. V. D. Plas (1993), The Design And Diffusion Of Improved Cooking Stoves, *The World Bank Research Observer*, 8(2), 119 -141.
- Black, T., and P. Harvey (1976), A Report On A Contraceptive Social Marketing Experiment In Rural Kenya, *Studies in Family Planning*, 7(4), 101-108.
- Chavangi, N. (1995), Participation and the Role of Women in Sustainable Development: The Kenyan Experience, in *Stove Images: A Documentation of Improved and Traditional Stoves in Africa, Asia and Latin America*, Brandes and Apsel, Frankfurt.
- D'Alessandro, U., B. Olaleye, W. McGuire, M. Thomson, P. Langerock, S. Bennett, and B. Greenwood (1995), A comparison of the efficacy of insecticide-treated and untreated bed nets in preventing malaria in Gambian children, *Transactions of the Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*, 89(6), 596-598.
- Dougherty, L., S. Kane, K. Smith, B. Winfrey, and S. Zellner (2004), *Social Marketing in Senegal*, Commercial Market Strategies Project, CMS Program Results and Implications, The US Agency for International Development, Washington DC.
- Eloundou-Enyegue, P., and D. Meekers (2004), From awareness to adoption: the effect of AIDS education and condom social marketing on condom use in Tanzania (1993-1996), *Journal of Biosocial Science*, (37), 257-268.

- Ergeneman, A. (2003), Dissemination of Improved Cookstoves in Rural Areas of the Developing World, Eritrea Energy Research and Training Center (ERTC), Goldman School of Public Policy, University of California, Berkeley.
- Geller, E. (2002), The Challenge Of Social Change: A Behavioral Scientist's Perspective, *Social Marketing Quarterly*, 8(2), 15-24.
- Karekezi, S. (2002), Poverty and energy in Africa - A brief review, *Energy Policy*, 30(11-12), 915-919.
- Karekezi, S., K. Lata, and S. Coelho (2004), Traditional biomass energy, *International Conference for Renewable Energies, Bonn*.
- Karekezi, S., and T. Ranja (1997), *Renewable energy technologies in Africa*, Zed Books and AFREPREN, Oxford U.K.
- Karve, A. (2005), *Biomass as Energy Source*, Alternative Energy Sources, VPM's Polytechnic, Thane.
- Khennas, S., T. Anderson, A. Doig, and D. Rees (1999), *Rural Energy Services: A handbook for sustainable energy development*, Intermediate Technology Publications, London, UK.
- Koshy C (1994), Cool Reception to Ambitious Programme, *Down to Earth*, 2(17), 5-7.
- Kotler, P., G. Armstrong, J. Saunders, and V. Wong (1999), *Principles of Marketing*, Prentice Hall Europe.
- Kotler, P., and G. Zaltman (1971), Social Marketing: An Approach To Planned Social Change, *The Journal of Marketing*, 35(3), 3-12.
- Kuhnhenh, K. (2003), Environmental and socio-economic Impact of improved Stoves-The Case of the Tsootso Stove in Northern Namibia, Lund University, Lund, Sweden.
- Meekers, D. (2000), Going underground and going after women: trends in sexual risk behaviour among gold miners in South Africa, *International Journal of STD & AIDS*, 11(1), 21-26.
- Owsianowski, J., and P. Barry (2007), *Improved Cooking Stoves For Developing Countries*, FASEN (Improved Stoves Senegal), Dakar.
- Schellenberg, J., S. Abdulla, R. Nathan, O. Mukasa, T. Marchant, N. Kikumbih, A. Mushi, H. Mponda, H. Minja, and H. Mshinda (2001), Effect Of Large-Scale Social Marketing Of Insecticide-Treated Nets On Child Survival In Rural Tanzania, *The Lancet*, 357, 1241-1247.
- Sharma, S. (1993), *Improved solid biomass burning cookstoves: a development manual*, Regional Wood Energy Development Programme in Asia, Food and Agricultural Organisation, Bangkok.
- Theuri, D. (2005), *Rural Energy, Stoves and Indoor Air Quality: The Kenyan Experience*, Berkeley University, Oakland.
- Tucker, J. (1984), *Intermediate technology transfer and cultural appropriateness: the case of woodburning cookstoves in Upper Volta*, Training Manual T-40, Peace Corps Information Collection and Exchange, Washington DC.
- Walubengo, D. (1988), Boiling Point 15: Stove Progress in Kenya and Sri Lanka, *Boiling Point, HEDON (Household Energy Development Organizations Network)*, 15, 1-5.